

DEVELOPMENT OF GENDER-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS**Ronn Bryan M. De Salit**

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ABSTRACT

Foremost concern in the development of instructional materials today is the manner and means by which teachers design and formulate gender-based instructional materials as gender roles and gender differences along with gender equality, are continually surfacing in the teaching and learning landscape. This study described and examined teachers' considerations and elements used in the development of gender-based instructional materials. The study used a descriptive correlational research in order to examine how teachers developed gender-based instructional materials. Thus, the study was participated by 200 randomly selected public elementary school teachers in the Philippines. Results of the study showed that teachers highly considered gender-based instructional materials' relevance, its applicability and quality. Thus, the results revealed that teachers highly perceived that gender-based instructional materials should contained gender-responsive activities, gender-fair type of learning and inclusivity of learners' gender preferences. Apparently, the study found out that there was a moderate positive relationship between the considerations on the development of gender-based instructional materials in terms of relevance and their perceptions based on the principles of gender-responsive education for the development of gender-based instructional materials in terms of gender-responsive activities. Further, the study revealed that there was a moderate positive relationship between the considerations on the development of gender-based instructional materials in terms of quality and their perceptions based on the principles of gender-responsive education for the development of gender-based instructional materials in terms of inclusivity of learners' preferences. The study recommended the development of an intervention program to help teachers significantly develop and implement gender-based instructional materials in their teaching and learning process.

Keywords:

Development, gender-based, instructional materials, relevance, quality, gender-responsive, activities, inclusivity

INTRODUCTION

Gender-sensitive education is strongly advocated by the Department of Education (DepEd) whereas learners are given the opportunities to express their gender preferences in a more inclusive, fair and equal teaching and learning environment. The adherence to the gender equality principles are emphasized in a more critical actions which include the development of gender-based instructional materials. While teachers are consistent with the implementation and fundamental principles of gender-sensitive education, many of them possess less awareness on the design, development and implementation of gender-based instructional materials. In this line, instructional materials are considered as one of the primary learning resources which teachers used in order to deliver quality-based instruction which could potentially lead to the attainment of quality-based education. Further, the development of instructional materials is also a crucial factor to achieve effective and efficient teaching and learning process. It involved an immense use of creativity, innovation and relevance whereas teachers displayed their competence in the design and development of instructional materials. These materials aid teachers to ensure that retentive and meaningful learning process takes place. Common structure of instructional materials used among public schools in the Philippines are designed logically and are based on learners' needs, readiness and interests. In modern societal landscape, diversity of learners are observed as learners showed different skills, competence, level of thinking and the like. These differences are not only seen

as core causes of diversity. Gender-differences and different gender preferences are also important dimensions to consider when designing and developing a lesson across various subjects among basic education institutions. The development of learning materials which are grounded on the basis of gender-sensitive education is also a primary concern for teachers. To this effect, in the progressive spectrum of Philippine education system, teachers are regarded as the writers and creators of their instructional materials used in the teaching and learning process. They designed, developed and implemented these instructional materials aligned with the teaching standards and learning competencies of their subjects handled.

Consequently, the development of gender-based instructional materials with respect to gender-sensitive education is rarely considered by teachers specially among public elementary schools in the Philippines. Based from the collective observations of the researchers, most of their colleagues design and develop creative and relevant instructional materials but significantly put less emphasis on gender-sensitive and gender-equality principles. The methods and means by which teachers designed and developed their instructional materials are paramount concern to effect efficient instruction. However, showing less emphasis on the development of gender-based instructional materials may pose great instructional threats to inclusivity and fairness. At the core concept of inclusivity, it entails that all learners should be involved in the achievement of effective and efficient instruction regardless of their socio-economic status, gender preferences, level of understanding among others. In the conditions observed by the researchers, most teachers relied heavily on the structure of instructional materials. On one hand, the development of gender-based instructional materials put greater emphasis in the attainment of inclusivity in the teaching and learning process. Apparently, the context of gender-sensitive and responsive instructional materials were paramount concern in building sufficient understanding on inclusivity and equality (Sujarat et al., 2022). There was implied functions and importance of teachers in the development and pursuit of a gender-sensitive school environment where they were expected to developed gender-responsive learning resources in order to cater inclusivity and gender-sensitive instruction (Enoc & Gagani, 2021). In addition, teachers' perceptions towards responsive gender learning were classified as indicative on the development of gender-based learning resources (Perregrino et al., 2020). Further, teachers who implemented a holistic approach to mainstream gender equality by contextualizing and localizing learning activities have promoted inclusive education (Talon et al., 2020). On one hand, teachers implemented gender-inclusive learning resources were able to significantly provide equal and fair learning environment specially when they instituted gender-based learning materials within the teaching and learning process (Wijanarko et al., 2022). In this regard, the researchers examined a strong knowledge gap on the basis that most of the published researches only focused on the effects gender-sensitive learning resources and the structure of gender-based learning resources. Hence, failure to comprehensively examine the considerations and elements in the development of gender-based instructional materials. So, this study filled this knowledge gap.

In view of the foregoing conditions, this study described and examined teachers' considerations and elements used in the development of gender-based instructional materials. Significance of this study vested heavily on the importance of examining the considerations and elements to develop gender-based instructional materials. In addition, the study provided significant scientific insights on what teachers should consider in order to develop a highly impactful and meaningful gender-based instructional materials. Apparently, this study supported Sustainable Development Goals (Quality Education). As the study could provide empirical evidences in the development of gender-based instructional materials, teachers could absorb the same in order to institute more inclusive teaching and learning process. And, when inclusive education is evident in the teaching and learning process, learners could be properly engaged leading to active participation. In this regard, interactive exchange of ideas could be advanced leading to more retentive instruction. On one hand, this study also highlighted the need for the development of an intervention program to help teachers significantly develop and implement gender-based instructional materials in their teaching and learning process.

OBJECTIVES

This study described and examined teachers' considerations and elements used in the development of gender-based instructional materials among selected public elementary school teachers in the Philippines. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. How may teachers' considerations in developing gender-based instructional materials be described in terms of relevance, applicability and quality?

2. How gender-based instructional materials may be developed based on the principles of gender-responsive education as perceived by teachers in terms of gender-responsive activities, gender-fair type of learning and inclusivity of learners' gender preferences?
3. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' considerations in developing gender-based instructional materials and their perceptions for such development based on the principles of gender-responsive education?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' considerations in developing gender-based instructional materials and their perceptions for such development based on the principles of gender-responsive education.

METHODOLOGY

This study used descriptive correlational research design. Apparently, the descriptive aspect of the study was the determination on teachers' considerations in developing gender-based instructional materials in terms of relevance, applicability and quality and the identification of teachers' perceptions based on the principles of gender-responsive education in terms of gender-responsive activities, gender-fair type of learning and inclusivity of learners' gender preferences. On one hand, correlational aspect of the study fell on the examination if there would be a significant relationship between teachers' considerations in developing gender-based instructional materials and their perceptions for such development based on the principles of gender-responsive education. Further, the study used a researcher-made survey questionnaire as the main research instrument. This developed survey-questionnaire contained two (2) parts. For part 1, it contained items relating to the considerations of teachers in developing gender-based instructional materials while part 2 contained items relating to the perceptions of teachers based on the principles of gender-responsive education for the development of gender-based instructional materials. The study used a 4-Likert Scale. For part 1, it used a 4-Likert Scale such as: 4-Highly Considered, 3-Considered, 2-Moderately Considered and 1-Not Considered. Meanwhile, for part 2, similar scale was used which employed different verbal descriptions such as: 4-Highly Perceived, 3-Perceived, 2-Moderately Perceived and 1-Not Perceived. The developed survey-questionnaire was subjected to validation and internal consistency measure. In validation process, the researchers sought the guidance and expertise of three (3) professionals who possessed doctorate degree in educational management, instruction and supervision. Expert-validators marked an "Outstanding" comments relative to the developed items which meant that the developed survey-questionnaire were aligned on the established research objectives of this study. Thereafter, the researchers subjected their developed survey-questionnaire to pilot test which was participated by non-included respondents who consisted of thirty (30) public elementary school teachers. Items under part 1 obtained a Cronbach Alpha result of .781 which signified that items under the same part were "Acceptable." In addition, items under part 2 gained a Cronbach Alpha result of .813 which also signified that these items were "Acceptable." Further, the researchers sent a letter of invitation among the respondents after they have posted a "Call for Participants" in their personal social media accounts. When they have already reached the interests of their targeted respondents, they deleted such post for purposes of ending such call. Then, they sent a formal invitation to the interested teachers through their personal social media accounts. Once agreement was reached in line with their respondents' participation, an online orientation was conducted by the researchers in order to enlighten them with the context, nature and objectives of this present study. Also, informed consents were distributed before the actual data gathering procedure took place. The researchers sent a Google Form link containing their developed survey-questionnaire on their respondents' social media account specifically on their Messenger accounts. Thus, once all the data have been collected, the researchers organized and stored gathered raw data using MS Excel. Hence, the researchers used relevant statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation and general weighted mean which enabled them to quantify their respondents' responses relative to their consideration in developing gender-based instructional materials and their perceptions based on the principles of gender-responsive educations. In addition, the researchers used Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) which enabled them to measure if there would a significant relationship between teachers' considerations in developing gender-based instructional materials and their perceptions for such development based on the principles of gender-responsive education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the basis of inclusivity within the educational landscape in the Philippines, gender differences and gender-equality were significant principles which teachers should adhere to. In providing inclusive, relevant, fair and equitable education for Filipino learners, their gender roles, preferences and differences formed the core part of gender-responsive and gender-based education principles. This does not end on the principles, actual implementation of actions involving instructional related activities surrounding gender-sensitive and gender-responsive education should be essentially acted upon primarily by teachers who served as the main implementers of curriculum. Instruction within the parlance of pedagogy does not only involved the strategies, methods and styles used by the teachers, the design, development and implementation of instructional materials advanced the efficiency and effectiveness of instruction across various subjects in basic education. One of the surfacing trends in the country's educational system today is the provision of inclusive and quality-based education, these two underlying fibers under the country's educational system are critical dimensions to proceed with optimum learning experiences. Learning does not only measure on the its impact to learners' existence but also the manner and methods by which holistic structure of education should be placed as common frontiers.

- 1. Teachers' Considerations in Developing Gender-Based Instructional Materials.** The result showed teachers highly considered relevance (wm=3.71), applicability (wm=3.62) and quality (wm=3.62). The results showed that teachers placed strong emphasis on relevance of gender-based instructional materials. This implied that teachers should focus on the diverse background of their learners and consider how gender-based instructional materials to be developed would influence their learners' learning experiences. In this line, relevant activities and tasks to be contained for the development of gender-based instructional materials could possible enhance engagement and promote inclusive learning since such materials to be developed would relate to the current needs and interests of learners specially in line with their gender roles and gender differences. In other words, relevance in the development of gender-based instructional materials would significantly pose greater interests for learners who may have different gender identities. On one hand, applicability aspect in developing gender-based instructional materials was also highly considered by the teachers. This signified that teachers considered that effectivity the gender-based instructional materials to be developed, responding to various situations or contexts as directly experienced by their learners. Hence, applicability of gender-based instructional materials to be developed should be placed within the shape and context of learning competencies written on existing curriculum. Apparently, emphasis on applicability of gender-based instructional materials indicated these materials should not only fit within the curriculum standards but also could be adapted to different teaching methods and learning styles. In others, applicability of the gender-based materials to be developed should also be flexible to address learners' needs specifically in line with the contexts of gender differences and gender-responsive education. Meanwhile, quality of gender-based instructional materials was also highly considered by the teachers as essential considerations. The result signified that high-quality gender-based instructional materials would be essential for effective and efficient teaching and learning processes. The result also indicated that teachers highly considered that the focus of gender-based instructional materials to be developed vested on the best forms of activities and learning to be contained thereto thereby preventing stereotyping, conventional views on learners' gender differences and gender bias. Results of the study supported the study of Indrawati et al. (2024) gender-based digital module was beneficial for teaching effectively fostering inclusivity and active participation of the learners. Also, similar study showed that integration of gender-inclusive materials emphasizing real-world application and interactive tools could foster holistic learning processes. Hence, the study implicated that teachers should be conscious on the importance of gender considerations for the development of their instructional materials. Thus, school administration should also put premium emphasis on relevance, applicability and overall quality of gender-based instructional materials through the conduct of technical workshops and trainings so that development of gender-based materials could be placed as significant fiber in the development of teaching and learning process under the ever-evolving educational landscape in the country.
- 2. Teachers' Perceptions on the Development of Gender-Based Instructional Materials Based on Gender-Responsive Education Principles.** The results showed that teachers highly perceived gender-

responsive activities ($w_m=3.91$), gender-fair type of learning ($w_m=3.90$) and inclusivity of learners gender preferences ($w_m=3.89$) were essential elements to be contained for the development of gender-based instructional materials. Teachers' perceptions on emphasizing gender-responsive activities for the development of gender-based instructional materials were highly considered which indicated that recognition on the learning activities that actively address the different needs and experiences of learners across all gender was important element in the design and development of gender-based instructional materials. The result further implied that importance of placing gender-responsive activities for the development of gender-based instructional materials could create an equitable learning environment. On one hand, the result also signified that teachers highly perceived the importance of gender-fair learning whereas to develop an effective gender-based instructional materials, they should prioritize the inclusion of equal opportunities for participation and access to the developed gender-based resources. In addition, the result showed that gender-fair learning as important element in the development of gender-based instructional materials would enable teachers to create fair and balanced approached to learning that would also empower their learners and engage them actively. Apparently, teachers highly perceived that gender-fair type of learning could reduce or eradicate gender bias and disparities within their teaching and learning process. Further, the result showed that teachers highly perceived that inclusivity of learners' gender preferences for the development of gender-based instructional materials would address broad spectrum of gender identities and expressions within the teaching and learning process. Apparently, the result also signified that emphasizing learners' gender preferences for the development of gender-based instructional materials, supportive environment and a sense of belonging among learners would be effected. Thus, teachers' high perceptions in recognizing learners' gender preferences for the development of gender-based instructional materials underscored higher level of inclusivity and learners' engagement. Results of the study supported the study of Trifunovic and Petrovic (2014) which concluded that the analyzed educational material served as the function of developing gender sensitivity, the principle of gender equality was respected in the selection of material and the distinguished gender characteristics went beyond traditional gender pattern. The study implicated that school administration involving school heads and teachers should practically integrate gender-responsive activities and gender-fair learning practices through the development of highly relevant, applicable and quality-based gender-based instructional materials so as to provide highly impactful academic outcomes and a more positive school climate among basic education institutions.

- 3. Relationship Between Teachers' Considerations in Developing Gender-Based Instructional Materials and Their Perceptions for Such Development Based on the Principles of Gender-Responsive Education.** The study found out that there was a moderate positive relationship between the considerations on the development of gender-based instructional materials in terms of relevance and teachers' perceptions based on the principles of gender-responsive education for the development of gender-based instructional materials in terms of gender-responsive activities ($r=.399$). Thus, the hypothesis, "There is no significant relationship between teachers' considerations in developing gender-based instructional materials and their perceptions for such development based on the principles of gender-responsive education," was rejected. This suggested that as teachers perceive the relevance of instructional materials to be higher, their recognition of the importance of gender-responsive activities also increases. The result also implied that teachers who prioritize the relevance of gender-based instructional materials are more likely to understand and value for activities that respond to the diverse gender identities. On the other hand, the study also found out that there as a moderate positive relationship between the considerations on the development of gender-based instructional materials in terms of quality and their perceptions based on the principles of gender-responsive education for the development of gender-based instructional materials in terms of inclusivity of learners' preferences ($r=.363$). "There is no significant relationship between teachers' considerations in developing gender-based instructional materials and their perceptions for such development based on the principles of gender-responsive education," was rejected. This suggested that as teachers' perceived quality of instructional materials increases, so does the recognition of the importance of inclusivity in addressing learners' gender preferences. Thus, the result implied that teachers who would value high-quality materials as they would develop gender-based instructional materials could reflect and accommodate

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the diverse gender identities and preferences of their learners. Results of the study supported that study of Nilapantjuran (2024) which concluded that the validity and practicality of gender-based interactive e-modules as learning resources were found as innovative approach which helped increased learners' interests in learning. Similar study also showed that through gender-based instructional materials relevance and quality, enabled teachers reduced gender bias within the teaching and learning process.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researchers expressed their sincerest gratitude to their loved ones, friends, colleagues and all individuals who have helped them complete this scholarly work. Above all, they are eternally grateful to God in the Highest who is and forever would be, the greatest source of wisdom, strength, compassion and diligence in constructing knowledge for the benefit of mankind.

CONCLUSION

At the basis of inclusivity within the educational landscape in the Philippines, gender differences and gender-equality were significant principles which teachers should adhered to. Teachers highly considered relevance, applicability and quality in the development of gender-based instructional materials in the teaching and learning process. In addition, teachers highly perceived that gender-based instructional materials should be developed based on the principles of gender-responsive education that strongly underscored gender-responsive activities, gender-fair type of learning and inclusivity of learners' gender preferences. Apparently, as teachers perceive the relevance of instructional materials to be higher, their recognition of the importance of gender-responsive activities also increases. Also, as teachers' perceived quality of instructional materials increases, so does the recognition of the importance of inclusivity in addressing learners' gender preferences.

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